

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №3 (17)

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О журнале

*Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.*

*Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.*

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SURGICAL APPROACHES TO RECURRENT VENTRAL HERNIAS AFTER SURGERY**Gaziev K.U.**

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Resume. The results of surgical treatment of recurrent postoperative ventral hernia (POVH) using synthetic endoprotheses have been studied. A retrospective uncontrolled study of the treatment results of 24 patients operated on for recurrent POVH, aged 62.5 ± 2.8 years, was carried out. Prosthesis were placed in the intermuscular space in 8 patients, in the preperitoneal space - 6 and intraabdominal space - 10. No specific wound complications were observed. The follow-up periods ranged from 4 months to 9 years. Recurrences of POVH - in 2 (8,3 %) patients. The cause of recurrences was tearing of the endoprosthesis edge from the place of its fixation. Repeated operations were performed. One patient with acute myocardial infarction died in the early postoperative period.

Key words: recurrent postoperative ventral hernia, prosthetic hernioplasty, endoprosthesis.

ОПЕРАЦИЯ ДАН КЕЙИНГИ ҚАЙТАЛАНУВЧИ ВЕНТРАЛ ЧУРРАЛАРДА ЖАРРОҲЛИК ЁНДАШУВИ**Газиев К.У.**

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Резюме. Сунъий эндопротезлардан фойдаланган ҳолда операциядан кейинги қайталанувчи вентрал чурани (ОКВЧ) жарроҳлик йўли билан даволаш натижалари ўрганилди. ОКВЧ бўйича операция қилинган, ўртача ёши $62,5 \pm 2,8$ йил бўлган 24 нафар беморнинг даволаниши натижалари ретроспектив назоратсиз таҳлил қилинди. 8 беморда протезлар мушаклараро соҳада, 6 беморда қорин парда олди соҳасида ва 10 беморда қорин ичида жойлаштирилди. Яра билан боғлиқ махсус асоратлар кузатилмади. Кузатув даври 4 ойдан 9 йилгача бўлган. 2 нафар (8,3 %) беморда ОКВЧ қайталаниши кузатилди. Қайталаниши сабаби — эндопротез четининг маҳкамлаш жойидан ажралиб кетиши бўлган. Қайта операциялар ўтказилди. Юрак инфаркти билан оғриган бир бемор эрта операциядан кейинги даврда вафот этди.

Калит сўзлар: қайталанувчи операциядан кейинги вентрал чура, протезли ҳерниопластика, эндопротез.

ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К РЕЦИДИВНЫМ ВЕНТРАЛЬНЫМ ГРЫЖАМ ПОСЛЕ ОПЕРАЦИЙ**Газиев К.У.**

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Резюме. Изучены результаты хирургического лечения рецидивной послеоперационной вентральной грыжи (ПОГ) с использованием синтетических эндопротезов. Проведено ретроспективное неконтролируемое исследование результатов лечения 24 пациентов, прооперированных по поводу рецидива ПОГ, средний возраст которых составил $62,5 \pm 2,8$ года. Эндопротезы были установлены в межмышечное пространство у 8 пациентов, в прелбрюшинное — у 6 и в внутрибрюшное — у 10. Специфических осложнений раны не наблюдалось. Сроки наблюдения варьировали от 4 месяцев до 9 лет. Рецидивы ПОГ выявлены у 2 (8,3 %) пациентов. Причиной рецидивов явилось отрыв края эндопротеза от места его фиксации. Выполнены повторные операции. Один пациент с острым инфарктом миокарда скончался в раннем послеоперационном периоде.

Ключевые слова: рецидивная послеоперационная вентральная грыжа, протезная герниопластика, эндопротез.

Introduction. Due to anatomomomomorphologic changes in the area of hernia gate [2] the plastic stage in the treatment of recurrent postoperative ventral hernia (POVH) is accompanied by certain technical difficulties. Various techniques of prosthetic hernioplasty using polymeric materials are generally accepted in the treatment of primary and recurrent POVH [10, 12]. And only in the presence of small POVH with a diameter of up to 3 cm, local tissue plasty is acceptable [12]. Despite the achieved technical possibilities in

the treatment of POVH, the risk of hernia recurrence remains high. Thus, according to The Ventral Hernia Working Group (VHWG), within 5 years of follow-up after surgery for POVH, the rate of reoperation after the first recurrence is 24%, after the second recurrence - 35%, after the third recurrence - 39% [8].

Purpose of the study. Investigate the results of surgical treatment of recurrent POVH using synthetic endoprostheses.

Material and methods. From 2014 to 2023, prosthetic hernioplasty using mesh endoprostheses for POVH was performed in the surgical department of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center in 77 patients, of which 24 patients (31.2%) had recurrent POVH: 22 females and 2 males. The mean age of the patients was 62.5 ± 2.8 years. The distribution of patients with recurrent POVH, according to the Chevrel - Rath (1999) classification [9], is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS (Chevrel-Rath, 1999)

M/L	W2			W3	W4		Total
	R1	R2	R4	R1	R1	R3	
M1	9	-	-	2	1	-	12
M2	2	1	1	2	-	2	8
M3	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
L4	-	-	-	1	1	-	2
Total	13	1	1	5	2	2	24

16 patients were hospitalized routinely, 8 patients were hospitalized for emergency indications for impinged recurrent POVH.

In 22 patients, various techniques of local tissue plastics were performed during previous surgeries. In 1 patient (R2) the previously performed operations were: local tissue plasty - 1 operation, prosthetic hernioplasty with polypropylene mesh endoprosthesis - 1 operation. Another patient (R4) had: local tissue plasty - 2 operations; plasty with de-epithelialized skin flap according to V.N. Yanov - 1 operation; prosthetic hernioplasty with polypropylene mesh endoprosthesis - 1 operation.

The majority of patients (16 patients) had one or another concomitant pathology (CHD, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, etc.) or their combination, which required correction under the therapist's supervision.

Prophylaxis of thromboembolic complications was performed according to the indications to all. Antibiotic prophylaxis was performed by a single intravenous injection of 1 g of cefotaxime 45 minutes before the operation.

Combined anesthesia was used in 17 patients: general anesthesia with elements of neuroleptanalgesia and artificial lung ventilation; peridural anesthesia was used in 7 patients.

The plastic stage of the operation is presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

PLASTIC STAGE OF SURGERY

MWR	Plastic options						Total
	Intermuscular placement		Preperitoneal placement		Intraabdominal placement		
	sublay	inlay	sublay	inlay	sublay	inlay	
M1W2R1	2	2	2	-	2	1	9
M1W3R1	1	-	-	-	-	1	2
M1W4R1	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
M2W2R1	-	-	-	-	1	1	2
M2W2R2	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
M2W3R1	-	1	-	-	-	1	2
M2W2R4	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
M2W4R3	-	-	1	-	1	-	2
M3W2R1	1	-	-	1	-	-	2
L4W3R1	-	-	1	-	-	-	1
L4W4R1	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
Total	5	3	4	2	5	5	24

A polypropylene mesh endoprosthesis (Lintex, St. Petersburg, Russia) was used in all cases.

According to The Ventral Hernia Working Group (VHWG), currently there are no unified recommendations on the variants of endoprosthesis placement in surgical treatment of postoperative and recurrent ventral hernias. The VHWG recommends prosthetic hernioplasty with intermuscular placement of the prosthesis, as well as "components separation" type operations (Ramirez operation) as the most optimal variants of surgical interventions for this pathology. Transposition of rectus muscles and restoration of the abdominal white line is an obligatory stage of these types of surgeries [8]. However, "components separation" operations are rather traumatic and cannot be recommended for their widespread use.

The European Society of Herniologists (EuraHS) recommends the following variants of prosthesis placement: in the onlay option, the prosthesis is placed over the sutured aponeurosis, with the subcutaneous fatty tissue being cut away from the aponeurosis over a certain area; in the inlay option, the edges of the prosthesis are fixed butt to the edges of the hernia gate; at intermuscular placement the vagina of rectus abdominis muscles is opened, the mesh endoprosthesis is placed in front or behind the rectus muscles; at preperitoneal placement the prosthesis is placed in the preperitoneal space; at intraabdominal placement the endoprosthesis is placed in the abdominal cavity.

The variant of plasty with partial covering of the prosthesis with aponeurosis is recommended to be referred to as bridging technique [11].

In our practice, we distinguished the variants of endoprosthesis placement (onlay, sublay, inlay) depending on the width of the hernia gate (W), and the depth of prosthesis placement (intermuscular, preperitoneal, intraabdominal), which is associated with the possibility of isolating the layers of the anterior abdominal wall in the area of the hernia defect [3].

Results and discussion. Due to the pronounced anatomomorphologic changes in the hernia gate area (disruption of anatomical layers, scar tissue changes) [3, 4] the endoprosthesis placement in the preperitoneal space was possible in 6 out of 24 operated patients (sublay mesh endoprosthesis placement - in 4 patients; inlay - in 2 patients). In 8 patients the endoprostheses were located intermuscularly (sublay - 5; inlay - 3 patients), and transposition of the rectus abdominis muscles was performed in 3 of them. Intraabdominal placement of the endoprosthesis as the least traumatic variant of plasty was applied in 10 patients (sublay - in 5 patients; inlay - in 5 patients). These were mainly elderly patients with concomitant pathology. Drainage of postoperative wounds was not performed.

The duration of hospital stay after the operation amounted to 8.5 ± 1.9 days. There were no specific wound complications in all operated patients.

The follow-up periods ranged from 5 months to 9 years. From the number of operated patients (24 patients) recurrences were noted in 2 (8,3%). The cause of recurrences was the tear of the endoprosthesis edge from the place of its fixation. Both patients were reoperated. In both cases, prosthetic hernioplasty with intraabdominal placement of the endoprosthesis was used (inlay - 1; sublay - 1 patient). One of these 2 patients died in the early postoperative period. The cause of death was acute myocardial infarction.

Conclusions. 1. The development of anatomomorphologic changes in the hernia gate area makes intermuscular and intraabdominal placement of the mesh endoprosthesis in recurrent POVH the most reasonable and technically feasible.

2. Prosthetic hernioplasty with the use of mesh endoprosthesis remains a reliable method in the treatment of recurrent POVH and is accompanied by a rather low (8.3%) frequency of recurrences in late and distant periods.

References:

1. Repeated operations in patients with recurrent hernias using synthetic endoprostheses / Belokonev V.I., Pushkin S.Y., Zhitlov A.G. [et al] // Theses of the scientific conference "Actual issues of herniology", October 31 - November 1, 2012. - M., 2012. - C. 34. (in Russian)
2. Results of treatment of recurrent midline abdominal hernias / A.A. Botezatu // Theses of the scientific and practical conference "Actual issues of herniology", October 31 - November 1, 2012. - M., 2012. - C. 47. (in Russian)
3. On the treatment of the postoperative ventral hernias / Lembas A.N., Tampey I.I., Ivanchenko V.V. [et al. [et al.] // Izvestiya vysshee obrazovaniya vysshee obrazovaniya. Volga region. Medical sciences. - 2011. - № 2 (18). - C. 9098. (in Russian)
4. Retromuscular plasty of the abdominal wall with synthetic endoprostheses for hernias / Parshikov V.V., Khodak V.A., Petrov V.V., Romanov R.V. // Bulletin of experimental and clinical surgery. - 2012. - Vol. 5. - P. 213218. (in Russian)
5. Timoshin, A.D. Resolution of the jubilee scientific conference "Actual issues of herniology" / A.D. Timoshin, A.V. Yurasov, A.L. Shestakov // Surgery. - 2007 - № 7 - C. 80. (in Russian)

6. Gaziyev, K. (2023). Features of the tactics of treatment in adult patients with postoperative abdominal hernia. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences*, 1(4), 158–161.
7. Incisional ventral hernias: Review of the literature and Recommendations regarding the grading and technique of repair / Breuing K., Charles E. Butler, Ferzoco S. [et al.] // *Surgery*. — 2010. — Vol. 148, № 3. — P. 544-558.
8. Chevrel J.P. Classification of incisional hernias of the abdominal wall / Chevrel J.P., Rath A.M. // *Hernia*. — 2000. — Vol. 4. — P. 7-11.
9. Operative treatment of ventral hernia using prosthetic materials / Han J.G., Ma S.Z., Song J.K., Wang Z.J. // *Hernia*. — 2007. — Vol. 11. — P. 419–423.
10. EuraHS: the development of an international online Platform for registration and outcome measurement of ventral abdominal wall hernia repair / F. Muysoms, G. Campanelli, G.G. Champault [et al.] // *Hernia*. — 2012. — Vol. 16. — P. 239-250.
11. Sanders D.L. The modern management of incisional hernias / Sanders D.L., Kingsnorth A.N. // *BMJ*. — 2012. — № 344. — P. 37-42.